

UNLOCK THE POWER OF EARTH OBSERVATION DATA WITH TERRASCOPE AND EOPLAZA

Martine Paepen (martine.paepen@vito.be), **Bram Janssen** (bram.janssen@vito.be), **Pratichhya Sharma** (pratichhya.sharma@vito.be), **Dennis Clarijs** (dennis.clarijs@vito.be)

VITO, Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium

Abstract

This paper highlights how the Terrascope platform and services add value to earth observation (EO) datasets. It shows how a single platform enables access to high-quality EO services for various applications and EO data while lowering the barrier for service providers, researchers, students, and private and public entities. Terrascope provides a carefully curated set of standardized orchestrators, including OpenEO, and a large processing environment that allows users to easily create a service on top of the available datasets. Additionally, Terrascope EOplaza provides an online marketplace built on top of the existing Terrascope platform that acts as a one-stop shop for earth observation products and related services. With the positioning of EOplaza as the base for the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem's online store, the platform aims to support users on a European scale. Users can easily access the data via OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) standardized web services (WMS, WMTS, WCS and OpenSearch) and via the Terrascope catalogue service based on open source and COTS components. The Terrascope EO Catalogue meets all the requirements for a modern and standard-based catalogue which can serve as the metadata catalogue within all kinds of projects where it is crucial to search easily within a huge amount of data records no matter where the data and applications are deployed, in a private, public or hybrid cloud environment.

At the conference we will present the status of Terrascope and EOplaza and future challenges of introducing such platforms.

Key Words: Earth Observation, Terrascope, EOplaza, Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, OpenEO, Catalogue, Sentinel, PROBA-V MEP, Mission Exploitation Platform, PROBA-V, GeoJSON, STAC, OGC, Network of resources

INTRODUCTION

Earth Observation data is growing exponentially and are frequently made open and freely available. However, selecting among these data, processing them, and developing operational value-added services can take time and effort. End-users with limited knowledge frequently get confused, whereas service providers struggle with high IT investments (both hardware and software), EO domain knowledge, and an understanding of the EO business ecosystem. To address this, Terrascope was conceived as the Belgian Collaborative Ground Segment to ESA, funded by BELSPO and built by VITO Remote Sensing in 2017. It provides a common ground for not only access to raw Sentinel and Belgian heritage EO data but also access to their products and processing power. Terrascope offers a range of tools and services for data discovery, visualization, and analysis, including web-based mapping tools, data processing tools, and API access to data and services. It combines scalable processing resources, a large EO data archive (+9 PByte), and a rich set of tools. The platform is intended to support a wide range of users, including researchers, policymakers, and industry professionals, in sectors such as agriculture, forestry, water management, and environmental monitoring. The new EOplaza provides an online marketplace that serves as a one-stop shop for on-demand earth observation products, and algorithms. It allows service providers to publish and share their services with the broad user community of Terrascope.

Terrascope includes an EO catalogue service to provide access to available EO data products. The EO catalogue service is based on open-source and COTS components. Elasticsearch is used for storing the collection and product metadata in GeoJSON format with respect to OGC standards (OGC 17-084, OGC 17-003, OGC 17-047 and OGC 13-026).

TERRASCOPE

The Terrascope platform is the Belgian Collaborative Ground Segment assigned to BELSPO where VITO acts as the designated entity. It provides easy access to Copernicus Sentinel satellite data, their products, various webservices and cloud processing capacity. The PROBA-V Mission Exploitation Platform (MEP), as an ESA pathfinder project, has served as the basis for Terrascope. PROBA-V MEP complements the PROBA-V user segment which is hosted by VITO and offers an operational exploitation platform on the PROBA-V data, correlative data and derived products [1] , [2] ,[3] ,[4] .

The mission of Terrascope is providing easy access to satellite data and products for a wide range of users, including researchers, policymakers, and commercial entities, with a main focus in the Belgian tissue. With a focus on promoting the use of remote sensing data and products in a variety of applications and assisting decision-makers by promoting sustainable development. As a comprehensive platform, it offers a variety of Earth Observation data products to support decision-making in various fields. These data products include optical satellite data from missions such as Sentinel-2 etc., which are useful for applications such as land cover mapping, vegetation monitoring, and urban planning. Additionally, Terrascope provides access to Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data, which can be used for applications such as monitoring of ice and ocean surfaces, detection of changes in land cover, and disaster management. The platform also provides access to atmospheric data, including data on aerosols, greenhouse gases, and air quality, which are useful for monitoring air pollution and climate change. Finally, Terrascope offers access to elevation data, including Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) data, which is important for applications such as flood mapping and urban planning [5] , [6] .

In addition to Earth Observation data products, Terrascope offers cloud processing capacities such as Virtual Machines (VMs) and Jupyter Notebooks, which allow users to process and analyse data on the platform itself without needing specialized hardware or software. The VMs are pre-configured with software and tools commonly used in Earth Observation data processing, such as QGIS, GDAL, and Python libraries for data analysis, including OpenEO. This enables users to perform complex data processing tasks without the need for high-performance computing resources or specialised software [6] .

The Terraviewer, a web application [10] built on top of TerraScope, can be used to display and explore the different datasets provided by the platform. The targeted user groups for this portal range a wide spectrum, supporting both expert users with GIS experience and non-expert users mainly interested in viewing the available data and comparing different layers. In addition to satellite imagery, it provides access to other data layers, such as land cover, bio-physical parameters, and agricultural parcels, which can be overlaid onto the imagery to provide additional insights. The Terraviewer provides several components to further explore and exploit the available data. Next to the general viewing capabilities it is possible to export what you see as an image format, compare different dates and/or layers and download data products and its metadata after authentication [7] ,[8] .

Figure 1: Terraviewer displaying Sentinel 2 natural color image, infrared image and NDVI

EOPLAZA

Terrascope provides a carefully curated set of standardised services that allows users to not just create their own services on top of the available datasets easily but also to publish and share them in an open-source platform called EOplaza. Terrascope EOplaza was launched as a component of Terrascope with the aim of creating

reusable code that can run on different platforms, not binding users to a single platform. It provides an online marketplace built on the existing Terrascope platform that serves as a one-stop shop for earth observation products, which hosts over a dozen different services [9] , [10] .

Each of the services available in EOplaza is labelled with a maturity level that tells a user exactly what to expect in terms of quality and performance. These levels also encourage service providers to onboard their services from a prototype level to gather feedback from the community to a fully verified, validated or operational level, which could enable them to monetize the services [11]. Therefore, EOplaza allows each individual Terrascope user to publish, share and monetize their services for free in a straightforward manner, allowing the user to expose their service to a larger audience.

Each registered user receives 1000 credits each month, with the option to subscribe for more credits, allowing users to choose the appropriate access level based on their specific requirements. The user also has the possibility to share credits amongst members of the same organisation. During the execution of a service, a certain number of credits will be deducted based on several metrics, such as resource consumption.

Figure 2: EOplaza interface showing some available services

In addition to a public service offering, the EOplaza has built-in billing and reporting capabilities. With this capability, service providers have no longer to deal with service's financial and legal aspects, allowing them to focus on their service and harvest the platform's benefits. With the potential to grow in a broad range of areas in the future, the services in the EOplaza currently focus on monitoring crop growth, detecting changes in vegetation, assisting farmers in optimising crop management practises, monitoring water resources, detecting changes in land covers, environmental parameters, and many more. These services can be executed by every Terrascope user, either directly via one of the OpenEO client libraries [12] or the OpenEO online web editor [13] . Though the user should have basic programming knowledge when using the client-based method, the online web editor is simple and does not require any programming skills. The editor interface is simple and user-friendly, making it a valuable tool for researchers, businesses and policymakers involved in environmental monitoring and agricultural and urban planning, among other things.

With the positioning of EOplaza as the base for the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem's online algorithm store, the platform aims to support users on a European and global scale. The ability to scale up quickly and efficiently

makes it possible for EOplaza to process and analyse vast amounts of data in real time. This is particularly important given the increasing volume of Earth observation data from satellites and other sensors.

EO CATALOGUE

Terrascope together with other exploitation platforms and virtual research environments find their origin in providing easy access to exponentially growing Earth Observation datasets. They serve the paradigm of 'bringing the users and their algorithms and services to the data' and no longer 'bringing the data to the users'. Though the real core of these services remains the data and the success of the platforms is highly dependent on the easiness of finding and accessing the data.

Within Terrascope the users and services can easily access the data via Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standardized web services (WMS, WMTS, WCS and openSearch) and via the Terrascope EO Catalogue service based on open source and COTS components. Elasticsearch is used for storing the collection and product metadata in GeoJSON format with respect to OGC standards (OGC 17-084, OGC 17-003, OGC 17-047 and OGC 13-026). The catalogue is designed using microservices and doesn't rely on a relational database system anymore which ensures simple maintenance and scalability and facilitates straightforward deployment in cloud environments.

A Terrascope catalogue Python client allows users to integrate the Terrascope OpenSearch API in a Python application. This client facilitates searching collections and products. Downloading data over HTTP(S) is also supported which can be useful when the user is not working on a Terrascope Virtual Machine or Notebook. The API is fully described on the VITOBelgium Github repo [14]. The source code is publicly available and a Notebook [15] shows how to use the Python client. Next to the OpenSearch service, the EO Catalogue supports a basic STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs) API [16].

The catalogue integrates with an external IdP authentication system (Keycloak) which enables authentication using social media accounts and integration with federated communities like EduGAIN enabling easy integration in a European Network of Resources (NoR) [17]. COTS reporting tools such as Kibana, Grafana and Tableau are used to provide comprehensive reporting based on download statistics in the Elasticsearch backend.

The Terrascope EO Catalogue is developed and deployed as a modern and standard-based catalogue with the aim to serve as the metadata catalogue independently on where the data and applications are deployed, in a private, public or hybrid cloud environment.

CONCLUSION

To face the challenges of the exponential growth of heterogeneous EO data volumes and to ease the exploitation of these massive amounts of EO-data, the VITO EO Catalogue and Long Term Archive are integrated in both the PROBA-V Mission Exploitation Platform and Terrascope which provide a comprehensive infrastructure offering data distribution, data viewing/analysis and on-demand processing supporting vegetation and agricultural related and wider environmental EO applications. By designing a solution which can be deployed both on a private cloud and on a public cloud hosting relevant data, the solution can address big data which goes beyond the capabilities of a single data centre. Furthermore, expert users can make use of powerful Web based tools and can self-manage virtual machines to perform their work on the infrastructure at VITO with access to the complete data archive.

Terrascope and its EOplaza marketplace provide free and open access to high-resolution satellite imagery of the Earth's surface, intending to promote greater transparency and collaboration in agriculture, sustainability, and environmental monitoring areas. The project uses data from the European Space Agency's Sentinel satellites and offers a range of tools and resources for processing and analysing the data. Furthermore, by providing a common platform for users to utilize and share these services, EOplaza serves as a valuable hub for accessing and collaborating on earth observation services. It offers a range of valuable services that can significantly benefit the earth observation research and application community. This makes that the Terrascope platform succeeds in its mission to democratize access to valuable resources that was once limited to a small group of experts. Terrascope

EOplaza is positioned as the base for the future Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem's online store which will support Copernicus data and service users on a larger scale [18] .

The impact of these integrated platforms for the user community has been high and has completely changed the way of working with the data. It opened the large amount of time series of valuable EO-data to a larger community of users.

REFERENCES AND HYPERLINKS

- [1] <http://proba-v.vgt.vito.be/>.
- [2] <https://proba-v-mep.esa.int>.
- [3] Proba-V Mission Exploitation Platform, Remote Sensing Journal, Technical Note, 2 July 2016, <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/8/7/564>
- [4] Proba-V MEP Leaflet for developers, https://proba-v-mep.esa.int/sites/proba-v-mep.esa.int/files/documents/mep_fact.sheets_finalweb.pdf.
- [5] <https://terrascope.be/>
- [6] <https://docs.terrascope.be/>
- [7] <https://viewer.terrascope.be/terrascope/>
- [8] <https://terrascope.be/en/news-events/getting-started-eo-viewer-set-your-preferences>
- [9] <https://terrascope.be/en/news-events/new-data-and-services-2023>
- [10] <https://portal.terrascope.be/>
- [11] A new collaboration platform for EO data and services | Vito remote sensing | 2023, <https://blog.vito.be/remotesensing/terrascope-eoplaza>
- [12] OpenEO Introduction, <https://openeo.org/documentation/1.0/#introduction>
- [13] OpenEO Web Editor, <https://editor.openeo.org/>
- [14] <https://vitobelgium.github.io/terracatalogueclient/index.html>
- [15] https://github.com/VITObelgium/notebook-samples/blob/master/Terrascope/Beginner/Terrascope_CatalogueClient.ipynb
- [16] <https://docs.terrascope.be/#/Developers/WebServices/TerraCatalogue/STACAPI>
- [17] <https://nor-discover.cloudeo.group/>
- [18] <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>